

THE ROLE OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS TO MAKE PERFECT HUMAN BEINGS

Navoi specialized culture

school teacher

Hamidova Dilchiroy Shamsitdinovna

Annotation: The article talks about the connection of music with education and the importance of music lessons in education. This article discusses the professional skills, innovative activities, psychological knowledge and culture of the music teacher.

Key words: music teacher, professional skill, mature generation, spirituality, music culture music, method, art, taste, aesthetics, music culture, art, intelligence, listening to music.

Music education is one of the main aspects of the education of sophistication, it teaches to appreciate the beautiful things around in the correct perception, equips a person with a high taste and forms a spiritual worldview. "Music expresses human feelings, hopes, desires in its own artistic language and actively affects human feelings. Music is both a science and an art."

Since music is considered a complex psychological and physiological process, vocal - choral works in music lessons are considered the most effective form of teaching students for moral - aesthetic education. Students' attention while listening to music his attention increases, his memory and speech develop, his worldview is formed, his activity increases, and he feels pleasure when he listens to his favorite music.

The implementation of music education in human development directly depends on the educational methodology, and the methodology of music education has its place in the series of sciences. This discipline studies the laws of music education in order to further improve the content and methods of music education relies on the generalized experiences of aesthetics, musicology, physiology, and psychology in its institutions. The methodology of music education has a direct

impact on the content and methods of education, especially in connection with the disciplines of aesthetics and musicology.

The essence of the methodology of music education, the art and culture of music is important for the young generation, and the development of this science is compatible with the improvement of education and the art of music in society. This subject is based on general principles such as consciousness, artistic and technical development, these principles serve to develop students' musical abilities, to strengthen their interest in music, and to educate them in their artistry.

The methodology of music education is considered a part of pedagogy, and as a pedagogic science, it summarizes the theoretical parts of the experimentally tested works - methods, methods, tools, and presents teaching methods that have given effective results in practice. These methods generalize the structure of the educational process and deal with the solution of separate and integral tasks included in it. **The Importance of Music in Education** Our guide to the importance of music in education highlights a string of vital benefits children get from receiving musical instruction from an early age.

Music is arguably the most life-enriching academic subject of them all. A universal language that triggers emotional responses and kickstarts creativity like no other, music is a fundamental pillar of arts education.

This article outlines the far-reaching benefits of music that stretch way beyond the subject itself and why music is an indispensable part of any academic programme.

Art and morality. These two spiritual phenomena are so strongly connected that one cannot fully exist without the participation of the other. Both of them can be called anthropology, only they reflect and study not human organs, like anatomy, but human moral - aesthetic and spiritual virtues, that is, his attitude to goodness and beauty, evil and ugliness. Therefore, the existence of art outside of ethics is impossible, and at the same time, ethics without art is deprived of propaganda and loses the character of activity. After all, the eternal and eternal main theme of art is

the struggle between good and evil, the emergence and solution of all other human problems serves as an assistant for the disclosure of this theme in the work of art.

Music and language have a deep and profound relationship. The link between musical instruction and better language development in young children has long been established.

Musical training stimulates and trains the same part of the brain that deals with understanding language. Children who have some exposure to musical education will, therefore, have a greater understanding of tone and how different segments of speech align. It can also be incredibly useful if your child is learning a second language.

The teacher of music culture should analyze and generalize the young psychological characteristics of the students of each class, as well as the specific psychological characteristics of each student in the class, in the process of performing all their musical activities.

References:

1. Umurzakov, B. N., & Umurzakova, L. B. (2022). THE USE OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MUSICAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 3(03), 13-16.
2. Usmanova D., kizi Shodieva G. N. ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN THE UZBEK.
3. Shodieva, G. N. K. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 4-2), 1128-1131.
4. Do'smatov, D. qizi Shodiyeva, GN (2022, May). O 'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH.
5. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2022). THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER RELATED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE. YOUTH, SCIENCE,

- EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(2), 179-182.
6. Shodiyeva, G. N. K., & Dustmatov, H. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 234-237.
 7. Komilova, N. (2022). GENDERED LEXICON OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 192-194.
 8. Satvoldievna, U. D. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 40-45.
 9. Bakhtiyor, U. (2021). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN HUMAN CULTURE AND IN SOCIAL LIFE.
 10. Umurzakov, B. (2020). THE ROLE OF THE ART IN EDUCATION. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 29-2, pp. 4-5). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.
 11. Умурзаков, Б. Н. (2018). ФОЛЬКЛОР-ДРЕВНИЙ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫЙ ЖАНР СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY* (pp. 31-34).

Internet sources:

1. www.library.uz
2. www.ziyonet.uz
3. www.lex.uz